

RGB COLOR SPACE BASED MACHINE VISION SYSTEM FOR CLASSIFICATION OF GUAVA FRUITS

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Abstract:

In the present work, a general approach is developed to estimate the ripeness level of Guava fruit without touching it. This work deals with the study of using an artificial computer based vision system as a non-destructive instrument to analyze fruit ripeness stage. The cultivar chosen for this study is Guava fruit. This paper presents a simple method that uses a combination of digital web camera, computer, and self developed graphics software to measure and analyze the surface color of fruits. The method has also the advantages of being versatile and affordable. The images of the fruits can be displayed on computer screen or printed on paper for qualitative analysis of color and structure. Quantitative information such as RGB color distribution, Chromaticity coordinates according to CIE1931 standard and averages (in terms of L_* , a_* and b_* values) can also be determined readily.

Keywords: RGB Color, fruit ripeness, computer vision, guava fruit classification.

Introduction:

Sorting of fruits on the basis of their ripening stage has been an issue faced by producers as well as sellers due to the sheer volumes handled and the delicate nature of the fruit. In the case of agricultural products, good efforts and appropriate techniques are necessary to distinguish between various ripening stages of fruits when using machine vision for sorting [1].

The increased awareness and sophistication of consumers have created the expectation for improved quality in consumer food products. This in turn has increased the need for enhanced quality monitoring. Quality itself is defined as the sum of all those attributes which can lead to the production of products acceptable to the consumer when they are combined. Quality has been the subject of a large number of studies. The basis of quality assessment is often subjective with attributes such as appearance, smell, texture, and flavour, frequently examined by human inspectors. Consequently Francis (1980) found that human perception could be easily fooled. Together with the high labour costs, inconsistency and variability associated with human inspection generate the need for objective measurements systems. Recently automatic inspection systems, mainly based on camera-computer technology have been investigated for the sensory analysis of agricultural and food products. This system known as computer vision has proven to be successful for objective measurement of various agricultural and food products. Computer vision includes the capturing, processing and analysing images, facilitating the objective and non destructive assessment of visual quality characteristics in food products. The potential of computer vision in the food industry has long been recognized and the food industry is now ranked among the top 10 industries using this technology [2]. Recent advances in hardware and software have aided in this expansion by providing low cost powerful solutions, leading to more studies on the development of computer vision systems in the food industry. As a result automated visual inspection is under going substantial growth in the food industry because of its cost effectiveness, consistency, and superior speed and accuracy. Traditional visual quality inspection performed by human inspectors have the potential to be replaced by computer vision systems for many tasks [1-4]. There is increasing evidence that machine vision is being adopted at commercial level. This paper presents the latest developments and recent advances of computer vision in the food industry. The fundamental elements of the systems and technologies involved are also examined.

Color and texture are the fundamental character of natural images, and plays an important role in visual perception. Color has been a great help in identifying objects for many years. The process of color classification involves extraction of useful information concerning the spectral properties of object surfaces and discovering the best match from a set of known descriptions or class models to implement the recognition task [2]. Texture is one of the most active topics in machine intelligence and pattern analysis since the 1950s which tries to discriminate different patterns of images by extracting the dependency of intensity between pixels and their neighboring pixels [1-4] or by obtaining the variance of intensity across pixels [2-3]. Recently, different features of color and texture are combined together for their applications in the food industry [5]. Color features have been extensively applied for guava fruit quality evaluation mostly for defect detection and grading. For instance, color features of each pixel in images obtained in three components of RGB spaces could be successfully used for grading of guava fruits on the basis of their ripening stage.

This paper describes the development of a low cost machine vision system using webcams and image processing algorithms for classification and sorting of guava fruit. In this study, the main objective is to develop low cost machine vision system with appropriate algorithms to sort guava fruits with specific category of their ripeness as green, ripe, overripe and spoiled. The system was to be used for automated sorting and it is integrated with image acquisition, image processing, and decision making algorithm.

System development

The system used low-cost webcams that required no frame grabber hardware, thus making the overall system cheaper and flexible from the design point of view. The images are taken by low cost webcam made by Iball [model i-C12.0]. The Color images acquired in computer by self-developed image acquisition software programmed using LabVIEW2012 with Vision development suit. The RGB values are evaluated from images using express VI available in LabVIEW. From this RGB values the CIE1931 chromaticity coordinates are calculated and also tristimulus values are evaluated from it. The fuzzy logic based sorting algorithm is used. The decision making is achieved for showing the class of fruit on the computer screen as green, ripe, overripe and spoiled.

Figure 1 Block Diagram of system

Figure 2 Developed System

Image acquisition and illumination hardware

The iball made 12 mega pixel web camera is used for image acquisition. This camera has six white LED for illumination. The LED brightness is controllable through potentiometer is provided on interface cable. The LUX meter is used for this purpose. This LED used having color temperature near to white light. The spectral characteristics of illuminating source are characterized using sterllar Net miniature spectrometer systems and software. The spectral characteristics are shown in figure 3.

Figure 3 Spectral characteristics of illumination source

This plot indicates two peaks, lower peak has peak wavelength of 445.88 nm and upper peak has peak wavelength of 565.77 nm. The CCT in the range of 5000 °K to 8000°K. This illumination system provides a uniform light intensity over the fruit sample plane as shown in figure 3.40.

Figure 4 Fruit under webcam with integrated light illumination source

A digital web camera iball i12 was located vertically at a distance of 10 cm from the sample. The angle between the camera lens axis and the lighting sources was around 45° . The experimentation with this illumination system is performed inside a close room whose internal walls were painted with dark color to avoid the light reflection.

Fuzzy logic based pattern recognition VI

In the present application, model for classification of guava fruits is developed using the fuzzy logic and mean RGB color values of fruit surface. The complete software module is developed image acquisition, pre-processing and fuzzy based pattern recognition. The image acquisition, illumination method, image segmentation is already explained in above sections of this chapter. The two modules were developed for prepackaging and storage shelf-life based classification of guava fruits.

The mean RGB values of each class of fruit were used to train the classifier. The fuzzy logic module is designed and implemented in LabVIEW using fuzzy system designer. Figure 5 shows the front panel user interface of developed software for guava fruit classification using fuzzy logic.

Figure 5. User interface of fuzzy logic based classifier VI

The developed system starts the process by capturing the fruit's image using an iball webcam. The feature extraction process is achieved using the image processing express VIs available in LabVIEW12 with vision development suit. The ROI image was extracted from acquired image. The mean RGB values from ROI of image is evaluated using Image Color Histogram VI. This includes the mean of each color plane. Figure 6 Shows block diagram of sorting Process.

Figure 6. Block diagram of sorting and grading process

The fuzzy logic module consists of following processes.

1. FIS Editor
2. Membership Function Editor
3. Rule Editor
4. Rule Viewer
5. Surface Viewer

The process starts with deciding the system inputs and outputs followed by the definition of input and output membership functions. Finally, the rules are constructed using IF-THEN statements using rule editor. The system works according to the rules set by the expert. Hence this is a critical step in the grading process. The rule and surface viewer are the graphics that are used to view the built system.

Experimentation with developed system

The developed machine vision based fruit sorter system is used for pre-packaging classification of guava fruits into four classes. 100 fruits samples of each ripening class were used for experimentation. The 50% of the fruit images from each group were used to train the PARC module and the remaining 50% fruits used for testing. The images of training set samples were captured at various times of the day for the each class. This method increase the data set variability and represent a more realistic scenario. The RGB color space and CIE 1931 chromaticity coordinates are used.

The classification accuracy obtained using developed system for the four classes of guava fruit is presented in Table 1

Table 1 Experimental Observations

Ripening state	No. of samples		Classification		performance %
	Training	Testing	Expert	System	
Green	50	50	50	50	100
Ripe	50	50	50	40	80
Overripe	50	50	50	44	88
Spoiled	50	50	50	46	92

Result and Conclusion

The average efficiency achieved using developed classifier system is about 90%, if human grading taken as reference level is assumed to be 100% accurate. However, 10% variation is also due to individual judgment of human-graders in perceiving the ripening level of fruit during manual grading, which of course is inevitable. The repeatability of the developed system is found to be 100% from rigorous experimental work.

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